

INTEGRATION PROCESSES IN THE INNOVATION ENVIRONMENT OF CLUSTERS

Ruhsora Hasanova Rasuljon kizi - student of accounting and audit,
faculty of economics, Ferghana State University,
Fergana, Uzbekistan

Abstract: *The beginning of scientific research on clusters in our country began in 2000 [18, 8], and scientific and practical work in this regard was initiated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of our country. It began with the implementation of large-scale reforms in all areas to increase the competitiveness of the country's economy by deepening, modernizing and diversifying the main industries. Several concepts related to these processes, such as technopolis, technopark, and cluster, have entered our way of life.*

Key words: *clusters, innovative, integration, production, modern, globalization.*

Introduction. Integration should be seen as an inevitable process in the modern economic space. Globalization stands out as a form of integration worldwide. There is also integration at the regional level. Integration to strengthen competitive positions has been known for over a hundred years. But decades of experience have shown that integration can be effectively used at the regional, sectoral or other mesolevels in setting strategic goals. The same can be said about the cluster. A cluster is a form of integration. At the same time, managed integration is not yet considered sufficient to realize the innovative goals of the participating enterprises.

Integration in an innovative environment is a more complex process, so the success of the cluster and participating enterprises largely depends on the effectiveness of managing this process. It should be understood that the goals of innovative development are often called strategic, depending on the period in

which they are assigned. Therefore, integration management should be implemented according to the cluster strategy.

Among many factors, there are innovative and integration processes as necessary conditions for the formation of a cluster. Based on this idea, the necessary conditions for the formation and development of innovative territorial clusters in Uzbekistan have been analyzed. However, the attitude to integration in cluster strategies can be analyzed from the point of view of the typology of strategies and their practical application in country clusters. In addition, the importance of choosing the right strategy for a cluster is considered in detail in the work "Management of cluster initiatives for the formation of an innovative strategy for the development of industrial clusters" [1]. In particular, Yu.V. Gusev and T.A. Polovova: "...cluster initiatives, which are the basis for creating clusters, are to a certain extent based not only on the unique characteristics of the network (content of activity, success factors, life cycle of innovations). Also, the potential opportunities for developing clusters in a strategic perspective based on the rational selection of priority areas of activity, the portfolio of innovative projects and the balance of interests of interested parties are explained in detail.

The strategy is implemented in different spheres of activity, which leads to its different interpretation in terms of concretizing the means, methods and mechanisms of achieving goals and tasks. Taking this into account, it is necessary to determine the semantic load of the strategy when designing the integration processes of the innovation environment of the cluster.

There are two opposing approaches to understanding strategy in the strategic planning literature. In the first case, a strategy is a clear long-term plan to achieve a goal, while strategy development is the process of finding a goal and making a long-term plan. This approach is based on the fact that all occurring changes are predictable, processes are determined in nature and can be fully controlled and controlled [2].

In the second case, the long-term strategy implies a qualitatively defined direction of development in terms of the size, means and forms of the enterprise's

activity, systems of production relations, as well as the company's place in the environment. According to this concept, strategy can be described as a chosen course of action, the activity and scope of which should lead the organization to achieve its goals. Activities in strategic planning are usually selected based on the results of a strategic analysis conducted using the BCG matrix and other matrices, as well as the results of the enterprise's SWOT analysis.

In business life, strategy refers to the overall concept of achieving the organization's goals, solving the problems facing it, and allocating the necessary limited resources. This concept (which corresponds to the second type of strategy) includes several elements. First of all, they include a general system and a system of goals consisting of specific tasks. Another element of strategy is a set of policies or rules that define specific organizational actions to achieve its goals. It should be noted that many approaches and even ideologies can be found that interpret strategy and its role in development. It does not matter which approach to strategizing is chosen from the point of view of taking into account the processes of integration in the strategy. The strategy has been developed for several years and is formulated with specific tasks in various projects, programs, and therefore for the cluster it should include goals and integration projects.

It should include the main model and mechanisms for activation of integration processes.

As revealed during the research, the typology of cluster strategies can be reduced to several main types with differences in the approach to development and growth:

1) "growth" - this strategy is aimed at comprehensively increasing production volumes, but does not exclude the development of innovative activities, the creation of new products and, often, the improvement of existing ones;

2) "integration" - in this case, the essence of the strategy can be defined as increasing profits through full vertical integration as the value chain is optimized;

3) "diversification" is a variant of the strategy, in which the main focus is on creating diversity by including participants of different industries in the cluster;

4) "reduction" - a strategy option in which the cluster has fulfilled its tasks and independent operation of enterprises is more profitable at the current stage of development of the regional or network economy [3].

The first three types of cluster should include integration clauses. And the integration should link to other rules, complement them or create value for the expected synergy.

The main characteristics of the strategy were highlighted by I. Ansoff in 1989 in the book "Strategic Management", and they apply to clusters:

- the strategy creation process is not completed immediately. This usually ends with the establishment of common paths, in which the promotion ensures the growth and strengthening of the position of the organization;

- formulation of strategies used in the development of the method of searching for strategic projects.

- The role of strategy in search, firstly, helps to focus on specific areas and opportunities; second, discarding all other options that do not fit the strategy;

- the need for an elimination strategy as soon as the actual direction of development leads the organization to the desired event;

- It is impossible to foresee all the opportunities that will be open during the development of specific types of activities in the process of strategy development. Therefore, it is necessary to use generalized, incomplete and incorrect information about various alternatives;

- more specific information is revealed when implementing one of the alternatives. However, this may call into question the validity of the initial strategic choice. Therefore, successful use of strategy is impossible without feedback;

- As for the selection of projects to be used as strategies and recommendations, they may seem the same. But these are other things. A benchmark is a goal to be achieved and a strategy is a means to that goal. A benchmark is a high level of decision making. If the leadership of the organization has changed, the strategy justified according to one set of basic principles will not be the same;

□ strategy and goals are interchangeable at certain points and different levels of the organization. Some performance parameters (for example, market share) can serve as a guide at one point, and at another - its strategy. In addition, since orientation and strategies are developed in a changing environment, there may be inconsistencies in documents when new directions are set, but it is necessary to improve the strategy, as well as the action plans in the divisions.

At the same time, there is no need to clearly define the cluster development strategy for the implementation of integration processes. In addition, a complicating factor in the classification of strategies in clusters is that most strategies cannot be identified separately by one of the characteristics . S.G. Tyaglov, P.A. As noted by Krasnokutsky, taking into account the specific characteristics of the activity of innovative clusters, it is possible to distinguish two extended strategies that fully describe the integration processes and allow them to be managed [4]:

- Strategies aimed at increasing the use of knowledge in existing clusters;
- Strategies aimed at creating new cooperation networks within clusters.

It should be added that choosing a strategy includes studying alternative directions of cluster development, evaluating and choosing the best strategic alternatives for implementation, using special tools, including quantitative forecasting methods, developing future scenarios and portfolio analysis is used. Implementation can be referred to as the development of programs, budgets and procedures, which can be considered as medium-term and short-term plans for the implementation of the strategy [5].

Another factor in the development of clusters, which is characteristic of the current stage of information technology development, is teaching the possibilities of combining digital technologies for management in the cluster. Salimyanova I. and Treyman M. consider digitization to be a part or the most important aspect of cluster innovation activity, analyze the relationship between innovation and digitization [6]. Joining this approach and digitization can be considered as an element of the modern stage of innovative activity.

Another important element of integration is deciding which resources participating businesses can pool. In the modern form, regardless of the attitude to innovation, the integration of property distribution in the cluster is already being implemented. This is reflected in the creation of community access centers, access centers, etc. But another promising level of integration can be provided by the description in the strategy and implementation of integration processes in relation to intellectual property objects. From this position, we can say that a strategy can contain a number of characteristics or levels of integration that affect it.

Another aspect that is important in the assessment of the state of the cluster from the point of view of the implementation of the strategy is to ensure the high economic indicators of the cluster enterprises and ensure its stability. For this, we can recommend using the approaches described in Yu. V. Gusev's work "Monitoring the development of clusters in the regional economy based on the assessment of economic stability" [1].

All leading clusters have strategic development goals for 5-10 years. Each of the clusters has from 40 to 1000 participants, the largest cluster in terms of infrastructure is "Tomsk Region Pharmaceuticals, Medical Equipment and Information Technologies" ITC. Each of the clusters produces innovative products. In 2016, the Ulyanovsk aviation cluster produced the largest volume of products.

Thus, to describe the current stage of development of clusters, a broad classification was formed, taking into account the existing characteristics of the system.

The study showed that currently there is no unified approach to the development of integration processes in the innovation environment of the cluster, as well as structures for managing intangible assets in the cluster structure.

Each cluster formulates and implements a strategy depending on the specific characteristics of its activity, the scale of infrastructure, existing intellectual property, etc.

The study of integration processes in existing clusters in Uzbekistan showed that the development of cluster policy in the state territories will undoubtedly have a positive effect on the country's innovative and economic potential.

At the same time, the leading clusters based on the classification are more innovative and stimulating and work in the local trade market, which indicates their activity in the territory of Uzbekistan. The main problem of developing the innovative environment of clusters in the country is the insufficient level of scientific and systematic support from the state. The analysis showed that all considered clusters are formed according to specific scenarios, often to solve specific problems or to receive federal assistance.

Initiation and implementation of integration processes in an innovative environment is also carried out without sufficient scientific justification. The joint activity of enterprises has a more traditional character of contractual relations, and from the point of view of methodological support, neither state normative documents nor cluster documents indicate how and how integration processes should be built.

The results of the research showed that in the innovation environment of the cluster, integration processes and management of intellectual property objects are carried out without proper systematization, and accordingly, there is a principle of attracting "effective" intellectual property resources for international competition along with material and intellectual property resources. financial resources are not implemented in clusters, which does not help to involve all available resources in integration processes.

Therefore, in order to increase the innovativeness and global competitiveness of the participating enterprises, there was a need to quickly develop methodological support for the development of integration processes, taking into account the management of intellectual property objects in the innovative environment of the cluster. It is necessary to purposefully develop the integration of enterprises participating in clusters, to ensure the availability of indicators, models and integration mechanisms in the cluster strategy.

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